

IMPROVEMENT OF ACID TREATMENT DESIGN TO PREVENT DETERIORATION OF RESERVOIR PERMEABILITY

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ABSTRACT

Currently, when developing oil and gas fields, it is increasingly necessary to face the problem of reducing production. The appearance of this problem is associated with various reasons, but to a greater extent it is expressed in a decrease in permeability, productivity coefficient due to a number of complications arising in the bottom-hole zone of the formation (BHZ) (mainly: absorption of drilling mud filtrate, salt deposition, suffusion of clay particles and the consequences of well repairs). There is a need to carry out work to increase or restore the filtration-capacity properties (FCP) of the formation.

Keywords: deposit, bottom-hole zone, acid treatment, drilling mud, well.

Acid treatment of BHZ is a solution to the problem of its contamination. Treatment of the bottomhole zone with acid compositions is the most common, relatively inexpensive and simple method of improving filtration characteristics and increasing well productivity, based on the interaction of an aqueous acid solution with minerals of the rock skeleton and introduced substances that block the flow paths of fluids. This method is effective at any stage of deposit development, it is used to influence both carbonate and terrigenous formations. In most fields of Western Kazakhstan, out of the total number of geological and technical measures (GTM), the share of acid treatments takes about 60-80%.

The Tengiz oil field, confined to the carbonate deposits of the Upper Devonian-Middle Carboniferous, is located in the southern part of the Caspian Geological province (the Caspian Depression).

Tectonically, the deposit is confined to the southern side of the Caspian Depression and belongs to the Karaton-Tengiz uplift zone.

The structure of Tengiz on the surface of Bashkir deposits (on the roof of the I object) is a high-amplitude isometric structure measuring 22 * 23 km. The arch of the elevation is flat, the wings of the structure are quite steep, the angles of inclination reach 20-25°. Near the beginning of the steep slope, the arch of the elevation is complicated by a chain of local elevations, with an amplitude of 100-200 m, forming a «rim». The elevations of Rome cover the north-western, northern and north-eastern parts of the arch, while in the south and south-west Rome is absent. The maximum amplitude of the ascent along the roof of the Bashkir tier reaches 1100 m. The structure of the Tengiz structure for the II and III objects is shown on the structural maps for the roof of the "vulkanika" and the roof of the Famensky tier, updated according to the results of drilling new wells.

In the three years that have passed since the previous Analysis of the development of the field, fifteen wells have been drilled, and no wells were drilled in 2017, and the results of drilling wells in 2015-2016 are reflected in sufficient detail in the work. The data obtained from these wells made it possible to clarify the

lithological and stratigraphic characteristics, effective oil-saturated thicknesses, filtration and reservoir properties of reservoirs within the studied part of the field, and did not significantly change the ideas about the structure of the reservoir and the thickness range of individual stratigraphic units or operational facilities.

According to information from 01.07.1986, oil reserves in the sum of categories C1+C2 amounted to 2648040 thousand tons (geological) and 1043901 thousand tons (recoverable). At the same time, the reserves of industrial category C1 oil amounted to slightly more than half (51.7%).

The calculation of geological reserves of oil and dissolved gas was carried out on 3 objects of calculation – I, II, III, corresponding to stratigraphic objects.

According to the I stratigraphic object, reserves were calculated separately for each sub-object - Bashkir, Serpukhov, Oka horizons, taking into account the allocated facies zones (platform, boundstone, slope).

For II, III stratigraphic objects, reserves are calculated separately for the platform and slope parts without allocating sub-objects.

The categoricity of geological reserves is justified in accordance with the degree of study: the data of testing and operation, laboratory studies of filtration and reservoir properties of rocks and reservoir fluids, field-geophysical studies of wells and the position of the VNK.

Hydrochloric acid treatments (HAT) at the field were carried out in the period 1988-1993, i.e. during the period of well development and initial operation from 2000 to 2001.

Total at the field in the period 1988-1993 HAT was carried out in 24 wells (36 wells-operations) and from 2000 to 2001 – in 4 wells (220, 463, 5056 and 7252). The work for each well was carried out according to an individual inflow optimization program.

As can be seen from the table, as a result of the work carried out, a positive effect was obtained in 24 wells (37 wells-operations) in the form of an increase in oil flow rates by 1.1 (sq.104) – 2.04 times (sq.113). According to research data, productivity coefficients

increased by 1.7 – 3 times. For individual wells, a gradual decrease in flow rates was observed, which led to the need for repeated exposure to HAT systems. At the same time, the well flow rates increased to the level of the flow rates received after the first HAT (№6, 12, 16, 26, 419). For three wells (sle.3 - perforation interval 4600-4798 m; sle.12 - perforation interval 4889-4914 m; sle.25 - perforation interval 4152-4197 m) the effect was not obtained due to low productivity of the layers. Acid hydraulic fracturing is a process of intensification of well productivity, in which acid is injected into the reservoir at a pressure sufficient to rupture the reservoir. As the acid moves along the resulting crack, part of the crack surface dissolves, forming a wire channel. The main purpose of acid fracturing is to form wire channels of sufficient length to allow more efficient drainage of the collector. With acid fracturing, it is possible to obtain a skin factor value from -4 to -6.

Acid hydraulic fracturing is performed in wells with low permeability and low productivity. Acid fracturing was performed both in platform wells and in boreholes of the marginal zone. Hydrochloric acid of 15-20% concentration was used. Usually, the treatment was carried out at an injection intensity of 2300-3500 l/min (20-30 barrels/min) in a volume of 250 to 500 m³ of acid.

The treatment of wells with hydrochloric acid has found the most widespread due to its comparative simplicity, cheapness and often favorable reservoir conditions for its use.

In oil-bearing rocks, limestones, dolomites or carbonate cementing substances are often present in varying quantities. Hydrochloric acid dissolves such rocks well, while the following main reactions occur. When exposed to limestone

When exposed to dolomite:

Calcium chloride (CaCl₂) and magnesium chloride (MgCl₂) are salts that are highly soluble in the carrier water of the acid formed as a result of the reaction. Carbon dioxide (CO₂) is also easily removed from the well, or at an appropriate pressure (over 7.6 MPa) it dissolves in the same water (Table 1).

It is known that 1 liter of a 15% acid solution contains 161.2 g of pure HCl. Therefore, it will take 4.53 liters of solution to dissolve 1 kg of limestone.

The holding time for acid neutralization for this deposit is established experimentally by measuring the concentration of acid in the spent and displaced to the surface through the tubing solution.

Usually the exposure time is 16 - 24 hours.

Table 1

Recommended volumes of HCl solution per 1 m of reservoir thickness

Breed	Volume of HCL solution, m ³ /m	
	during primary processing	during secondary treatments
Low - permeable thin - porous	0,4 - 0,6	0,6 - 1,0
Highly permeable	0,5 - 1,0	1,0 - 1,5
Fractured	0,6 - 0,8	1,0 - 1,5

Simple acid treatments are the most common, carried out by setting the HCl solution in the BHZ (Table 1).

With multiple treatments for each subsequent operation, the solvent capacity of the solution should increase by increasing the volume of the injected solution, increasing the acid concentration, as well as by increasing the injection rate. The initial concentration of the solution is 12%, the maximum is 20%.

Calculation of treatment of borehole with hydrochloric acid, initial data:

Depth H = 3800 m

Uncovered effective capacity of the carbonate reservoir h = 25 m

The inner diameter of the well D = 0,154 m

TUBING diameter d = 0,05 m

Determination of the required amount of chemicals.

For the given conditions, we assume an acid concentration of 8%. With an average rate of consumption of this acid of 1.2 m³ per 1 m of the treatment interval, the total volume of hydrochloric acid will be 1.2 m × 25 = 30 m³.

Calculation of the amount of chemicals and water.

Preparation of 6 m³ of 8% hydrochloric acid solution requires 1840 kg of 27.5% HCl and 4.38 m³ of water, and 30 m³ of 8% hydrochloric acid solution requires concentrated HCl:

$$W_k = \frac{1840}{6} \frac{30}{6} = 9200 \text{ кг}$$

and water:

$$V = \frac{4,38}{6} \frac{30}{6} = 21,9 \text{ m}^3$$

The amount of concentrated commercial hydrochloric acid for a 10% hydrochloric acid solution can also be found by the formula:

$$W_k = \frac{A \times W(B \ z)}{Bz(A \ x)}$$

where A=214 and B=226 are numerical coefficients for an acid of 8% concentration; x is the 8% concentration of hydrochloric acid solution; z is the 27.5% concentration of commercial acid; W=30 m³ is the volume of acid solution.

Conclusions. The main processing of the bottom-hole formation zone method for wells with carbonate fractured – porous reservoirs is hydrochloric acid treatment. There are various ways to influence hydrochloric

acid on the carbonate formation (baths, simple acid treatments, deep-directed, point-interval, etc.).

Most hydrochloric acid treatments can improve the permeability of the bottom-hole zone of the formation. Processing of zones remote from the borehole presents certain difficulties due to the impossibility of delivering hydrochloric acid to the depth of the formation. As a result of the high rate of acid reaction in the carbonate component of the formation, water is released in the bottom-hole zone, which is pushed into the depth of the formation by another portion of acid.

When using most methods of treating the formation with hydrochloric acid, hydrochloric acid is absorbed by the drained zones of the formation, and the non-working areas remain untreated. This explains the low efficiency of repeated hydrochloric acid treatments.

According to the calculations carried out, the preliminary flow rate of wells was determined.

The flow rate for well No. 12314 before the HAT was 5.1 t/day, after the HAT – 5.2 t/day. The duration

of the technological effect was 210 days. Additional production of 21 tons

The flow rate for well No. 12523 before the HAT was 5.4 t/day, after the HAT – 5.7 t/day. The duration of the technological effect was 153 days. Additional production of 45.9 tons

The flow rate for well No. 12899 before the HAT was 1.1 t/day, after the HAT – 2.2 t/day. The duration of the technological effect was 149 days. Additional production of 163.9 tons.

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